

WOMEN CONSUMERS PSYCHOLOGY TOWARDS USE OF PERSONAL HYGIENE PRODUCTS

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Abstract

Personal hygiene is the practice of keeping oneself clean and caring for oneself in order to promote general health and stop the transmission of infections. Maintaining one's own cleanliness is referred to as personal hygiene. All of the external body's parts need to be kept clean and in good condition for good personal hygiene. It is crucial for preserving both physical and mental wellness. Consumer psychology is the study of human behaviour regarding their buying patterns, customs, and preferences in relation to consumer products, including their reactions and preferences to the products. This concept aims to evaluate and understand consumers and the decision-making process. The use of hygiene products is rising due to the initiatives taken by Governing agencies to encourage the adoption of hygiene products by organizing health awareness campaigns to restrict spread of diseases. There are five types of personal hygiene; Hair Hygiene, Hand Hygiene, Oral Hygiene, Body Hygiene and Intimate Hygiene. The present research was conducted to study the psychology of women consumers towards the use of personal hygiene products. In this study their awareness for personal hygiene products and usage patterns were studied. Women consumers have psychological factors and psychological purposes in their minds behind the use or non-use of personal hygiene products. In this study, the various psychological factors that influence women consumers' use of personal hygiene products were investigated. The study is descriptive research based on primary data collected from 200 women consumers of personal hygiene products. From the study it is found that all women consumers were not using personal hygiene products but maximum women consumers were using personal hygiene products because they are aware about personal hygiene products and considered personal hygiene products are necessary for them. The psychological factors and psychological purpose play an important role in the acceptance of personal hygiene products in a varied proportion.

Keywords: Psychology, Personal Hygiene, Personal Hygiene Products, Women Consumer, Psychological Factors, Psychological Purpose.

INTRODUCTION

Consumer psychology is the study of human behaviour regarding their buying patterns, customs, and preferences in relation to consumer products, including their reactions and preferences to the products. This concept aims to evaluate and understand consumers and the decision-making process. Psychological factors influencing consumer behaviour such as demographics, personality, lifestyles, and behavioural variables like usage rates, usage occasion, loyalty, brand advocacy, and willingness to provide referrals (www.emotiv.com).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), hygiene refers to conditions and practices that help to maintain health and prevent spread of diseases. Maintaining one's own cleanliness is referred to as personal hygiene. Regular showering or bathing, hand washing, especially before handling food, keeping hair short or removing hair, wearing clean clothing, cleaning teeth, and trimming fingernails are all behaviours that are usually seen as proper hygiene practises (www.alliedmarketresearch.com).

Personal hygiene is the practise of keeping oneself clean and caring for oneself in order to promote general health and stop the transmission of infections. All of the external body's parts need to be kept clean and in good condition for good personal hygiene. It is crucial for preserving both physical and mental wellness. It helps to maintain personal hygiene and manage body odour. It aids in preserving one's health, upholding a favourable sense of oneself, fostering confidence, improving social connections, and promoting psychological well-being. The body offers a perfect environment for germs to flourish, increasing the risk of diseases for those with inadequate personal hygiene.

The global personal hygiene market was valued at \$508.5 billion in 2020 and is projected to reach \$720.7 billion by 2030 registering a CAGR of 3.6% from 2021 to 2030 (www.alliedmarketresearch.com).

Use of hygiene products is rising as a result of the growing influence of beauty and grooming among people. Governing agencies of several countries are undertaking initiatives to encourage the adoption of hygiene products by organizing health awareness campaigns and the availability of hygiene products is increased through various distribution channels such as supermarkets, hypermarkets, convenience stores and online stores.

Women are emotionally (psychologically) involved with personal hygiene product due to intrinsic and extrinsic. The intrinsic psychology is how she think about herself) and extrinsic is how she is perceived by others. The female personal hygiene product market is of high value, characterized by well-established behaviours. Women continue to be a valuable customer when it comes to personal hygiene products.

Personal Hygiene Products Growth Drivers

1. Rising Awareness about the Importance of Personal Hygiene

People are becoming more conscious of the value of maintaining good personal hygiene. People are becoming more and more aware of the value of maintaining good personal hygiene. Due to different health education initiatives run by healthcare facilities, information being spread through the media, and social media awareness, people are becoming more aware of maintaining good hygiene. These programmes help to clarify the relationship between personal cleanliness and general health. Apart from this, people are realising that maintaining excellent hygiene can lower their risk of disease, stop the spread of infections, and enhance their quality of life.

2. Increasing Focus on Health and Wellness

People are becoming more health-conscious and proactive about their well-being. They are focusing more on health and wellness due to the rising influence of social media on individuals. They are favouring a healthier lifestyle, which motivates them to purchase personal hygiene items and consistently practise cleanliness habits. In order to prevent the spread of illnesses and uphold general improved health, people are buying personal hygiene products like skin care, oral care, and intimate hygiene products.

3. Growing Urbanisation and Changing Lifestyles

Because of rising urbanisation, there is an increase in the use of hygiene products. Personal hygiene items that are portable and convenient are becoming more and more popular as a result of people's busy and tense lifestyles. They increasingly favour

portable and simple-to-use hygiene items. The market is expanding as a result of the rising demand for feminine hygiene products that are comfortable and convenient at work.

4. Increase of Disposable Income

Due to the wide spread of education to all corners of country and industrialization majority of population is engaged in job or various activities, which creates disposable income to the population.

Types of Personal Hygiene

1. Hair Hygiene:

Regularly washing and grooming hair keeps it clean, prevents dandruff, and maintains a healthy scalp. It removes oil and keeps a person looking clean and fresh.

2. Hand Hygiene

Hand washing is one of the most crucial personal hygiene practices. Regularly washing hands with an anti-bacterial soap for at least 20 seconds helps eliminate harmful bacteria and viruses and preventing the spread of illnesses.

3. Oral Hygiene

Taking care of your oral health involves brushing teeth at least twice a day, flossing regularly. Good oral hygiene prevents dental issues like cavities, gum diseases, and bad breath.

4. Body Hygiene

Showering or bathing daily helps keep the body clean, remove sweat, dirt, and bacteria, and prevent body odour. Antiseptic Liquid can be added to the bathing water in order to feel refreshed and clean. Using clean clothes and changing them regularly also falls under body hygiene.

5. Intimate Hygiene

Special care should be taken to clean intimate areas gently and regularly to prevent infections and maintain comfort.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the psychology of women consumer towards use of Personal Hygiene products.
2. To study the awareness level of women consumers towards Personal Hygiene products.
3. To study the psychological factors of women consumer for non-acceptance of Personal Hygiene products.
4. To study the psychological purpose of women consumer behind using Personal Hygiene products.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Psychology of women consumers are in favour of using Personal Hygiene products.
- H2: Psychological factors of women consumers plays an important role in usage of personal hygiene products.
- H3: Women consumers are using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose.

RESEARCH MATHODOLOGY

The present study is a descriptive research based on primary data containing various psychological parameters of women consumers toward use of Personal Hygiene products. The primary data has been collected from the women of Khandesh region of Maharashtra state. A structured questionnaire of 15 questions was developed to collect data from women of this selected area. Total 140 women those are ready to give response were selected by simple random sampling technique from the selected area. Data collect from these 140 women respondent was in the form of personal data as well as psychological response of women consumer for use of Personal Hygiene products. The collected data was analyzed by SPSS software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Respondent Profile Data

Sr. No.	Attributes	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age of Respondents	Up to 20 years	105	42.0
		20 to 35 years	85	34.0
		above 35 years	60	24.0
		Total	250	100.0
2.	Marital status	Unmarried	85	34.0
		Married	125	50.0
		Widow	40	16.0
		Total	250	100.0
3.	Education	Higher secondary	55	22.0
		Graduate	75	30.0
		Post Graduate	120	48.0
		Total	250	100.0
4.	Profession	Student	55	22.0
		House wife	90	36.0
		Service	85	34.0
		Self employed	20	8.0
		Total	250	100.0
5.	Monthly Income	Up to 20,000/-	45	18.0
		20,000 to 40,000/-	130	52.0
		Above 40,000/-	75	30.0
		Total	250	100.0

Table No.1 contains respondent profile data. The age group of 42% of women respondents was below 20 years old, while 34% were in the 20–35-year age group, and 24% were above 35 years old. The maximum of 50% of respondents were married, and 34% were unmarried. By profession, 36% of women respondents were

housewives, and 34% were in service. The 52% women respondents have their monthly income in the range of 20,000 to 40,000 rupees, while 30% have their monthly income above 40,000 rupees.

Table 2: Psychological thinking about Personal Hygiene Products

Sr. No.	Attributes	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Awareness of Personal Hygiene Products	No	31	12.4
		Yes	219	87.6
		Total	250	100.0
2.	Necessity of Personal Hygiene Products	No	30	12.0
		Yes	220	88.0
		Total	250	100.0
3.	Using Personal Hygiene Products	No	35	14.0
		Yes	215	86.0
		Total	250	100.0

Table no.2 shows the psychological thinking of women consumers about personal hygiene products. The 87.6% of women consumers were aware about personal hygiene products, and 88% of women consumers considered personal hygiene products necessary for them. The 86% women consumers are using personal hygiene products.

Table 3: Psychological Reasons for not using Personal Hygiene Products

Sr. No.	Attributes	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Allergy of Personal Hygiene Products	No	85	34.0
		Yes	165	66.0
		Total	250	100.0
2.	No faith on Quality of Personal Hygiene Products	No	105	42.0
		Yes	145	58.0
		Total	250	100.0
3.	Fear of Side Effects from Personal Hygiene Products	No	95	38.0
		Yes	155	62.0
		Total	250	100.0
4.	Personal Hygiene Product are Costly	No	95	38.0
		Yes	155	62.0
		Total	250	100.0
5.	Not feeling Need of Personal Hygiene Products	No	150	60.0
		Yes	100	40.0
		Total	250	100.0
6.	Shortage of time	No	190	76.0
		Yes	60	24.0
		Total	250	100.0

Table No.3 contains various psychological reasons for women consumers not using personal hygiene products. The 66% of women consumers were not using personal hygiene products due to allergies, while 58% of women consumers had no faith in the quality of personal hygiene products. The 62% of women consumers have a fear of side effects from personal hygiene products, and 62% are considering personal hygiene products are Costly. 40% of women consumers are not considering the need for personal hygiene products, and 24% have a shortage of time to use personal hygiene products.

Table 4: Personal Hygiene Product Usage Data

Sr. No.	Attributes	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Hair Hygiene Products	No	5	2.0
		Yes	245	98.0
		Total	250	100.0
2.	Hand Hygiene Products	No	40	16.0
		Yes	210	84.0
		Total	250	100.0
3.	Oral Hygiene Products	No	40	16.0
		Yes	210	84.0
		Total	250	100.0
4.	Body Hygiene Products	No	77	30.8
		Yes	173	69.2
		Total	250	100.0
5.	Intimate Hygiene Products	No	91	36.4
		Yes	159	63.6
		Total	250	100.0

Table No.4 contains the personal hygiene product usage data of women consumers. Hair hygiene products are used by 98% of women consumers, while 84% of women consumers are using hand hygiene products. Oral hygiene products are used by 84% of women consumers. Body hygiene products are used by 69.2% of women consumers. But intimate hygiene products were used by 63.6% of women consumers, which is less as compared with other types of hygiene products.

Table 5: Purpose of Using Personal Hygiene Products

Sr. No.	Attributes	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Medical Purpose	No	170	68.0
		Yes	80	32.0
		Total	250	100.0
2.	To increase Confidence	No	196	78.4
		Yes	54	21.6
		Total	250	100.0
3.	Feel Beautiful	No	155	62.0
		Yes	95	38.0
		Total	250	100.0
4.	Personal Care	No	115	46.0
		Yes	135	54.0
		Total	250	100.0
5.	Feel Younger	No	235	94.0
		Yes	15	6.0
		Total	250	100.0

Table No.5 contains various purpose of women consumers behind using personal hygiene products. The 54% of women consumers are using personal hygiene products for the purpose of personal care, while 38% of women consumers are using personal hygiene products to feel beautiful. The 32% of women consumers are using personal hygiene products for medical purposes, and 21% of women consumers are using personal hygiene products to increase confidence.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H0: Psychology of all women consumers are in favour of using Personal Hygiene products.

H1: Psychology of all women consumers are not in favour of using Personal Hygiene products.

The above hypothesis was tested with two test for two different variables. For single variable of using personal hygiene products was tested with Chi-Square Test and Using various personal hygiene products was tested with One Sample t-test at 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$.

Using Personal Hygiene Products			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
No	35	125.0	-90.0
Yes	215	125.0	90.0
Total	250		

Test Statistics	
	Using Personal Hygiene Products
Chi-Square	129.600 ^a
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 125.0.	

The significance value 'p' of the test is less than the α level 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and infer that the psychology of all women consumers are not in favour of using personal hygiene products. So, some women consumers were not accepting the use of personal hygiene products.

The same hypothesis was tested with One Sample t-test for the variables of personal hygiene products usage.

One-Sample Test				
	Test Value = 0			
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Using Hair hygiene products	110.458	249	.000	.980
Using Hand hygiene products	36.156	249	.000	.840
Using Oral hygiene products	36.156	249	.000	.840
Using Body hygiene products	23.653	249	.000	.692
Using Intimate hygiene products	20.858	249	.000	.636

The significance value 'p' of the test is less than the α level 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and infer that the psychology of all women consumers are not in favour of using personal hygiene products. From the mean difference it was proved that women consumers were using personal hygiene products in different proportions.

H0: Psychological factors of women consumers playing an important role in usage of personal hygiene products.

H1: Psychological factors of women consumers not playing an important role in usage of personal hygiene products.

One-Sample Test				
	Test Value = 0			
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Allergy of personal hygiene products	21.985	249	.000	.660
No faith on quality of personal hygiene products	18.543	249	.000	.580
Fear of side effects from personal hygiene products	20.156	249	.000	.620
Personal hygiene products are Costly	20.156	249	.000	.620
Not feeling need of personal hygiene products	12.884	249	.000	.400
Shortage of time	8.867	249	.000	.240

The above hypothesis was tested with One Sample t-test at 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$.

The significance value 'p' of the test is less than the α level 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and infer that the Psychological factors of women consumers not playing an important role in usage of personal hygiene products. From the mean difference it was proved that psychological factors of women consumers were playing varied roles in usage of personal hygiene products.

H0: Women consumers are using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose.

H1: Women consumers are not using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose.

The above hypothesis was tested with One Sample t-test at 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$.

One-Sample Test				
	Test Value = 0			
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Medical purpose	10.825	249	.000	.320
To increase Confidence	8.283	249	.000	.216
Feel Beautiful	12.354	249	.000	.380
Personal care	17.097	249	.000	.540
Feel Younger	3.987	249	.000	.060

The significance value 'p' of the test is less than the α level 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and infer that Women consumers are not using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose. They are using personal hygiene products for varied purposes.

CONCLUSION

- 1) The maximum women consumers were using personal hygiene products because they are aware about personal hygiene products and considered personal hygiene products are necessary for them. But all women consumers are not using personal hygiene products.

From the first hypothesis testing it is proved that the psychology of all women consumers are not in favour of using personal hygiene products, so they all are not using personal hygiene products.

- 2) There are various psychological factors of women consumers for not using the personal hygiene products. Mainly Allergy of Personal Hygiene Products, fear of side effects from personal hygiene products, personal hygiene products are Costly

and no faith in the quality of personal hygiene products are the psychological factors behind non-use of personal hygiene products by women consumers.

The hypothesis test of second hypothesis proved that the psychological factors of women consumers not playing an important role in usage of personal hygiene products. The psychological factors of women consumers are playing varied roles in usage of personal hygiene products.

- 3) Women consumers are not using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose. They are having varied psychological purposes behind use of personal hygiene products. Mainly they are using personal hygiene products for personal care, to feel beautiful and medical purpose.

From the hypothesis three testing it is also proved that women consumers are not using personal hygiene products for specific psychological purpose. They are using it for varied psychological purposes.

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